

Large scale modeling of seawater intrusion in a coastal aquifer: application to the North Sharon and Heffer Valley areas, Israel.

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ABSTRACT

Seawater intrusion, in the form of a wide transition zone from fresh water to seawater, is a well-known phenomenon occurring in most coastal aquifers, as a result of unbalanced freshwater extraction practices. The prediction of seawater intrusion resulting from planned water extraction scenarios is of crucial importance as it allows maximization of freshwater sustainable extraction, while preserving the coastal aquifer's viability by minimizing adverse salinization processes.

Seawater intrusion can be monitored by observation wells. However, the number of such wells needed for the construction of a reliable three-dimensional picture of the transition zone between fresh water and seawater would be so large that it is practically infeasible. Therefore, simulation models are used, in combination with the available observed data.

This work presents the development, application, and validation of a three-dimensional model, FEAS, for the simulation of seawater intrusion, formulated as a density dependant groundwater flow and salt transport problem in 3-D heterogeneous and anisotropic formations. FEAS was applied to the North Sharon – Heffer Valley region of the Israel coastal aquifer. This is a heterogeneous anisotropic aquifer, covering an area of over 300 km². The model was first calibrated to identify the values of its hydraulic parameters (hydraulic conductivity, porosity, specific yield, and replenishment coefficients). It was then run for flow and salt transport for three time periods: 1) 1800-1933, pristine conditions (prior to any pumping), in order to obtain a picture of seawater wedge prior to the aquifer exploitation; 2) 1933-1974 rapid development of pumping from the aquifer, and 3) 1975-2002 current conditions, with significant sea water intrusion. The results obtained at the end of the simulation periods were in satisfactory agreement with the available data. The model was then used for estimating the impact of a number of exploitation and replenishment scenarios.

1. BACKGROUND

The Israel coastal aquifer, hereafter ICA, is one of the major sources of the country's freshwater. This is a pleistocenic aquifer of varying thickness (from 200 m at the vicinity of the sea to less than 30 m at its eastern edges, approximately 15 km from the coast). Along the western border, up to 3-4 Km to the east, the aquifer is subdivided by clay layers. The aquifer is exploited means of over 1,200 pumping wells, which extract approximately 300 Million Cubic Meters per year. The main mechanism of replenishment are natural replenishment from rainfall and returning flow from irrigation. Artificial recharge of both freshwater and treated effluent, through both wells and infiltration ponds, is intensively practiced. The ICA is connected to the Mediterranean sea through its upper layers.

In a coastal aquifer such as the ICA, a contact zone between seawater and freshwater develops and is represented as a sharp interface or a transition zone. Unbalanced exploitation of freshwater within the aquifer is usually followed by seawater intrusion and salinization of pumping wells. A sound aquifer management requires tools capable of predicting the relationship between seawater and freshwater resulting from specific water abstraction scenarios. Water resources managers and planners have to face a design problem - seawater intrusion into the coastal aquifer, salinization of wells resulting from over-exploitation – and a hydrologic problem - understanding the seawater and salinization processes, locating the seawater intrusion extent interface and predicting the salinization. Since the 50's seawater intrusion has been represented as a sharp interface between seawater and freshwater. Location of the interface was found with a few number of wells drilled near the coast. The characteristic parameter was the interface toe.

This research was part of the Israel Coastal aquifer project, which was funded by the Water Commission. It included the construction and calibration of a two-dimensional horizontal model of flow and flow and seawater intrusion (assuming as sharp interface) for the whole ICA, construction and calibration of a three-dimensional model for the simulation of groundwater flow in the North Sharon and Emek Heffer area and development of a coupled density dependent groundwater flow and salt transport model – application to the the North Sharon and Emek Heffer are. Development of a dedicated software – FEASi as part of the Ph.D research of Quanlin Zhou at the Technion under the direction of Prof. Jacob Bear and Dr. Jacob Bensabat.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE COUPLED MODEL

Description of the seawater and freshwater interaction in a 3D configuration of a heterogeneous and anisotropic aquifer of regional size. The basic variables are the piezometric head and the salt concentration. Description of the salinity distribution within the aquifer (in the plane and vertically) resulting from sources of anthropogenic origin.

3. THE MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Sea water intrusion into coastal aquifers is a well known phenomenon and need not be discussed here (e.g., Bear et al., 1999). Until recent years, most models of sea water intrusion have been based on the "sharp interface approximation", combined with the "Ghyben-Herzberg assumption" (e.g., Bear, 1979), which, although not necessarily true, was considered simpler for solution. Although the sharp interface approximation is valid under

3.1 Variable density and viscosity

We shall express the flow model in terms of a *reference (fresh water) piezometric head*, $h_f(x, y, z, t)$, defined as

$$h_f = \frac{p}{\rho_{fw}g} + z, \quad (1)$$

using ρ_f as a reference density. We introduce a *normalized salt mass fraction*, $C(x, y, z, t)$, defined by

$$C = \frac{\omega - \omega_f}{\omega_s - \omega_f} \quad (2)$$

in which ω and ω_s denote the salt (or TDS) mass fraction (i.e., mass of the dissolved salt per unit mass of fluid) in water (= salt solution) and in sea water, respectively, and ω_f is the fresh water mass fraction, used as a reference mass fraction.

The constitutive equation that expresses the relationship, $\rho = \rho(p, \omega)$, between the fluid density, the pressure, and the salt mass fraction, is

$$\rho = \rho_0 \exp[\beta'_p(p - p_0) + \beta'_\omega(\omega - \omega_0)] \quad (3)$$

where ρ_0 , p_0 , and ω_0 are reference values of density, pressure, and salt mass fraction, respectively, $\beta'_p = (1/\rho)\partial\rho/\partial p$ is the coefficient of water compressibility (at constant salt mass fraction), and $\beta'_\omega = (1/\rho)\partial\rho/\partial\omega$ is a coefficient that introduces the effect of change in salt mass fraction on the fluid's density (at constant pressure). We select $\omega_0 = \omega_f$ (i.e., equal to the mass fraction of fresh water). The reference pressure is such that for fresh water at $p = p_0$, the density is $\rho = \rho_f$ as the density of fresh water is selected as a *reference density*.

The linearized approximation of (3) is

$$\rho = \rho_0 [1 + \beta''_p(p - p_0) + \beta''_\omega(\omega - \omega_0)] \quad (4)$$

where $\beta''_p = (1/\rho_0)\partial\rho/\partial p$ and $\beta''_\omega = (1/\rho_0)\partial\rho/\partial\omega$. We shall assume that for the range of pressures considered here, $\beta''_\omega |\Delta\omega| \gg \beta''_p |\Delta p|$, so that we may employ the approximation:

$$\rho = \rho_f (1 + \beta_c C), \quad \beta_c = \beta''_\omega (\omega_s - \omega_f) \quad (5)$$

where β_c may be referred to as a *density difference factor* (dimensionless). In spite of the above assumption, we do take into account the effect of pressure in the expression for the specific storativity appearing in the mass balance equation.

To introduce the effect of mass fraction on the fluid's dynamic viscosity, we use the constitutive relationship for dynamic viscosity in the form (Lever and Jackson, 1985):

$$\mu = \mu_f \mu_r = \mu_f (1 + 1.85\omega - 4.1\omega^2 + 44.50\omega^3) \quad (6)$$

in which the viscosity, μ_f , corresponds to $\omega = 0$, and μ_r is defined by (6).

3.2 Water flux equation

The *specific discharge relative to the solid*, $\mathbf{q}_r \equiv \phi(\mathbf{V} - \mathbf{V}_s) = \mathbf{q} - \phi\mathbf{V}_s$, is expressed by Darcy's law (Bear, 1972; Bear and Bachmat, 1990)

$$\mathbf{q}_r = \phi(\mathbf{V} - \mathbf{V}_s) = -\frac{\mathbf{k}}{\mu}(\nabla p + \rho\mathbf{g}\nabla z) \quad (7)$$

in which \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{V}_s denote the velocity vectors of the water and of the solid matrix, respectively, ϕ denotes the porosity, the second rank tensor, \mathbf{k} , denotes the permeability, and \mathbf{q} denotes the specific discharge vector. We assume here that $\mathbf{V}_s \approx 0$, $\mathbf{q}_r \approx \mathbf{q}$. In terms of h_f and C , Darcy's law is then rewritten as

$$\mathbf{q} = -\frac{\mathbf{K}_f}{\mu_r}(\nabla h_f + \beta_c C \nabla z), \quad \mathbf{K}_f = \frac{\rho_f g \mathbf{k}}{\mu_f} \quad (8)$$

with \mathbf{K}_f denoting the reference hydraulic conductivity.

3.3 Mass balance equation for water

For water of variable density, the general mass balance equation takes the form: (e.g., Bear, 1972, 1979; Bear and Bachmat, 1990)

$$\frac{\partial \phi \rho}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{q} - \phi \mathbf{D} \nabla \rho) + (\rho_R Q_R - \rho Q_P) \quad (9)$$

in which Q_R and Q_P , denote, symbolically, the rates of injection of water into and withdrawal of water from the aquifer (dims. 1/T), ρ_R denotes the density of the injected water, t is the time, and \mathbf{D} , a second rank symmetric tensor, denotes the *coefficient of dispersion* (dims. L²/T). When water is withdrawn and injected through (point) wells, the symbolic source and sink terms in (9) may, symbolically, be written as:

$$\rho_R Q_R = \sum_n \rho_{Rn} Q_{Rn}(\mathbf{x}_n, t) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_n) \quad (10)$$

$$\rho Q_P = \sum_m \rho_m Q_{Pm}(\mathbf{x}_m, t) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_m) \quad (11)$$

in which Q_{Rn} and ρ_{Rn} are the injection rate, and the density of the water injected through a well at point \mathbf{x}_n , respectively, and Q_{Pm} and ρ_m are the pumping rate and density of the water pumped through a well at point \mathbf{x}_m , and δ denotes the *Kronecker delta*. Note that (9) includes a term, $\mathbf{J}^{*\rho}$, denoting the *dispersive flux of the total fluid mass*, which can be rewritten in the form:

$$\mathbf{J}^{*\rho} = -\mathbf{D} \cdot \nabla \rho = -\rho_f \beta_c \mathbf{D} \cdot \nabla C \quad (12)$$

Very often we neglect this term

In view of the relationship $\rho = \rho(p, C)$, we make use of (4) and (8) to modify (9), rewriting it in terms of the reference piezometric head, h_f , and the normalized mass fraction, C , in the form:

$$S_0 \frac{\partial h_f}{\partial t} + \phi \beta_c \frac{\rho}{\rho_f} \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \left[\frac{(1 + \beta_c C)}{\mu_r} \mathbf{K}_f \cdot (\nabla h_f + \beta_c C \nabla z) + \phi \beta_c \mathbf{D} \cdot \nabla C \right] + \frac{\rho_R}{\rho_f} Q_R - (1 + \beta_c C) Q_P \quad (13)$$

in which $S_0 = \rho g (\phi \beta_p + \alpha)$ denotes the *aquifer's elastic storativity*, with α denotes the aquifer's (vertical) compressibility. Other forms are also possible.

3.4 Mass balance equation for the dissolved salts

For a fluid of variable density, the general mass balance equation for the TDS in the water can be written in the form:

$$\frac{\partial \phi \rho \omega}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\rho \omega \mathbf{q} - \phi \rho \mathbf{D}_h \cdot \nabla \omega) + \rho_R \omega_R Q_R - \rho \omega Q_P \quad (14)$$

in which \mathbf{D}_h denotes the *coefficient of hydrodynamic dispersion* (a second rank symmetric tensor), $\mathbf{D}_h = \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{D}_{diff}^*$, and \mathbf{D}_{diff}^* denotes the *coefficient of molecular diffusion in a porous medium*. In an *isotropic* porous medium, the *coefficient of dispersion*, \mathbf{D} , is related to the fluid's velocity and to the *longitudinal and transversal dispersivities*, α_L and α_T (dims. L), respectively, by

$$D_{ij} = \alpha_T V \delta_{ij} + (\alpha_L - \alpha_T) \frac{V_i V_j}{V} \quad (15)$$

in which δ_{ij} denotes the *Kronecker delta*.

The salt transport equation, (14), can be written in terms of the normalized mass fraction, C , with $\omega_f = 0$ (Bear, 1999; Zhou *et al.*, 2005):

$$\frac{\partial \phi \rho C}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\rho C \mathbf{q} - \phi \rho \mathbf{D}_h \cdot \nabla C) + \rho_R C_R Q_R - \rho C Q_P \quad (16)$$

Expanding the first-order derivatives in (16) and making use of the mass balance equation for water, (14), we can rewrite the transport equation in the form:

$$\phi \rho \frac{DC}{Dt} = \nabla \cdot (\phi \rho \mathbf{D}_h \cdot \nabla C) + \rho_R Q_R (C_R - C) \quad (17)$$

Altogether, we have to solve the variable density flow equation, (13), and the salt transport equation, (17), simultaneously, for the two primary variables: $h_f(x, y, z, t)$ and $C(x, y, z, t)$, making use of (5) and (6) to express ρ and μ , and (8) to express \mathbf{V} or \mathbf{q} .

3.5 Initial and boundary conditions.

The initial conditions for the variable density flow and salt transport equations are

$$h_f(x, y, z, 0) = h_{f0}(x, y, z), \quad C(x, y, z, 0) = C_0(x, y, z), \quad (18)$$

where $h_{f0}(x, y, z)$ and $C_0(x, y, z)$ are known distributions.

The conditions on the boundary segments (shown in Figure 1) for the flow equation, (13), neglecting the dispersive flux of the total fluid mass, are:

On AF	$q_n \equiv \mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0,$	(impervious bottom)
On EF	$h_f = h_{fp},$ or $\mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{n} = q_{np},$	(land-side lateral boundary)
On ED	$\rho q_n = -\rho_N N n_z + \frac{(\phi \rho - \theta_{w0} \rho_N)}{ \nabla F } \frac{\partial h_f}{\partial t}$	(phreatic surface)
On CD	$h_f = \zeta_{DE},$	(seepage face)
On BC	$h_f = \beta_c H_{sea},$	(sea bottom)
On AB	$h_f = \beta_c H_{FA},$	(sea-side lateral boundary)

where h_{fp} is the prescribed reference head on a Dirichlet-type boundary, q_{np} is the prescribed fluid flux on a second-type boundary, \mathbf{n} is the unit outward normal vector, with the components n_x, n_y, n_z in three dimensions, N is the rate of replenishment, ρ_N is the density of the replenishment, θ_{w0} is the irreducible water content assumed to prevail in the unsaturated zone, ζ_{DE} is the elevation at a point on the seepage face above sea level, H_{sea} and H_{FA} are the depth of sea water at a point on the sea bottom and the sea-side lateral boundaries, respectively.

The boundary conditions for the salt transport equation are:

$q_n^d \equiv -\mathbf{D}_h \cdot \nabla C = 0,$	On AF and DC
$C = 0$	On EF
$q_n^d = -\left(\frac{\rho_N}{\rho} C - C_N\right) \left(N n_z + \frac{\phi_{w0}}{ \nabla F } \frac{\partial h_f}{\partial t} \right)$	On ED
$C = 1,$	On AB

where q_n^d is the hydrodynamic dispersive flux normal to a 2nd- or 3rd-type boundary, and C_N is the normalized mass fraction in the replenishment water.

On the sea bottom boundary, BC, we may have either only landward flow from the sea, in which case the condition there is the same as on BA, or we may have both an inflow portion, MB, and an outflow portion, CM, separated by a point with zero-normal fluid flux. For the inflow portion, we usually employ either a third-type condition

$$q_n^d \equiv -\mathbf{D}_h \cdot \nabla C = (1 - C)q_n, \quad (19)$$

or a Dirichlet condition

$$C = 1 \quad (20)$$

For the outflow portion, the assumption is often made that the fluid concentrations on both sides of this boundary are identical (i.e., continuous). Since the fluid fluxes are also identical, the condition becomes a second-type condition:

$$q_n^d \equiv -\mathbf{D}_h \cdot \nabla C = 0. \quad (21)$$

The (moving) point M , between the inflow and outflow portions of the boundary, is unknown *a priori*. In a numerical solution, during each iteration, we check whether flow along the sea bottom is directed inward or outward, and then assign the appropriate boundary condition accordingly.

To overcome inconsistency That may occur on the outflow portion, we may assume the presence of a *buffer zone* on the sea bottom, which contains out-flowing water. We then take the density of this fluid into account when determining the head condition on this boundary. Iterations may be required in a numerical solution. The thickness of this buffer zone is a calibration parameter.

4. CONSTRUCTION OF THE MODEL FOR NSEH AREA

The values of the hydraulic parameters were taken from the groundwater flow model calibration. The lower sub-aquifers are assumed to be closed at the sea boundary. The western border of the model was located 1 km to the west of the coast. The computational mesh was highly refined along the coast (horizontally and vertically). The density parameter was assumed to be equal to 0.026. Horizontal dispersivity 5 m transversal dispersivity 0.5m. Figure 2, illustrates a plan view of the computational mesh, figures 3 and 4, present vertical cross sections of the ICA perpendicular and parallel to the coast.

4.1 Initial conditions of seawater intrusion

The use of the model requires initial conditions of groundwater and salinity concentration. It is impossible to create initial conditions of salinity with the available data. Simulation is used to obtain the initial conditions. The model was run for three periods: 1800-1934 (pristine conditions, prior to any water extraction), 1935-1974 (pumping development) and 1975-2000 (actual conditions), for which data on rainfall, pumping and injection is available.

4.2 Initial conditions of salinity within the aquifer

There are ~300 wells in the study area of the ICA for which data on salinity is available. The salinity picture was create following a stochastic simulation procedure (SISIM - sequential indicator simulation, Journel). Initial conditions on salinity were then created by merging the output of the model simulation and the stochastic simulation.

4.3 Model runs for the generation of initial conditions of seawater intrusion

1800-1934: model runs without pumping and using an average replenishment from rainfall. The output of this run was used as the input for the next one. 1935-1974: Development of the pumping in the area. Reconstitution was based on the available data and some assumptions regarding the operations of the wells. At the end of this process we obtained a picture of the salinity in the western edges of the aquifer.

4.4 Boundary conditions of salinity

Replenishment from returning freshwater irrigation: average salinity of the water produced within a reporting cell. Replenishment from returning treated effluent irrigation: salinity equal to ~500 mg/l. Salinity of replenishment from rainfall – 40 mg/l. Influx from the Eocene aquifer (north-east) with a salinity of 1000 mg/l.

5. SIMULATIONS RESULTS

Results of the simulation are illustrated on a vertical cross section perpendicular to the sea (Figure 5). In this cross-section contours normalized salt concentrations are illustrated at various simulation times (1934, pristine conditions, 1966 to 2000, various conditions of the water abstraction and replenishment).

Figure 6 displays a q-q plot of simulated versus measured salt concentrations at all times, at wells close to the sea. One can notice the relatively satisfactory agreement between measurements and simulations.

6. SUMMARY

An operational model for the simulation of groundwater flow and salinity transport (including seawater intrusion was built). The model is based on state of the art numerical technologies. It is capable to reproduce the major processes occurring during seawater intrusion and provide a three dimensional picture of the salinity bodies in the aquifer. The heterogeneity of the aquifer and the distribution of clay layers and lenses have a strong impact on the salinity distribution within the aquifer. The model allow to test scenarios of aquifer exploitation both from the quantitative and qualitative point of views.

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FIGURES

Figure 2: Plan view of computational mesh.

Figure 3: Vertical cross-section of the Israel coastal aquifer, perpendicular to the coast.

Figure 4: Vertical cross-section of the Israel coastal aquifer, parallel to the coast.

Figure 4: Normalized salt concentration at a vertical cross section, at various simulation times.

1988

2000

Figure 6: Measured versus simulation salt concentrations at wells along the coast.

